

SALBAGE

Sulfur-Aluminium Battery with Advanced Polymeric Gel Electrolytes

H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017

FET-Open – Novel ideas for radically new technologies

GA 766581

Type of action: RIA (Research and Innovation action)

Start date of the project: 01/11/2017

Duration: 36 months

Deliverable D.1.1

Launch of SALBAGE website, branding and logo

Project partners

LOGO	Partner full name	Acronym
	Albufera Energy Storage S.L.	AES
	University of Leicester	UoL
	Scionix Ltd.	Scionix
	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	CSIC
	Technische Universität Graz	TUG
	University of Southampton	UoS
	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet	DTU

Deliverable Name: Launch of SALBAGE website, branding and logo

Led by: AES

Partners: All

Date	Version	Author	Institution	Comments*
13/12/2017	01	Ana López Cudero	AES	Creation
19/12/2017	01	Ana López Cudero	AES	Final version
10/02/2019	02	Ana López Cudero	AES	Revision after evaluation: elimination of water mark. Revision of the part regarding Intranet

* Creation, modification, final version for evaluation, revised version following evaluation, final

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	2 / 9

List of Acronyms

Acronym	Description

Content

1	Introduction	4
2	Branding image	4
1.1	LOGO	4
1.2	Templates	4
3	Webpage	5
4	Social Networks	7
5	Conclusions and final remarks.....	9

Figure Index

Figure 1:	SALBAGE Logo	4
Figure 2:	Capture of the dedicated webpage	5
Figure 3:	Capture of the dedicated webpage featuring the Intranet Access	6
Figure 4:	Login in the intranet.....	6
Figure 5:	Intranet private area	7
Figure 6:	Capture of the Researchgate page.....	7
Figure 7:	Preview of the LinkedIn profile.....	8
Figure 8:	Preview of the Twitter profile.....	9

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	3 / 9

1 Introduction

Within the dissemination activities of the SALBAGE project, the creation of the branding image, logos and webpages was foreseen. In the same sense the inclusion of profiles in different social networks was proposed as a mean of reaching a greater public beyond the scientific community.

According to this, the first deliverable of the project gathers and presents all the above mentioned steps

2 Branding image

1.1 LOGO

A dedicated logo for the project was created and distributed among the partners. It is shown in figure 1. A first version was chosen among different possibilities and voted by a majority of the partners but it was further modified with the inputs of the partners till this final version was reached.

The Logo combines the colours of Sulphur (yellow) and Aluminium (grey) into a green battery, making reference to the main purpose of the SALBAGE project, the creation of a sustainable battery with the combination of Aluminium and Sulphur electrodes. In this very same sense, the letters corresponding to the aluminium as element in the periodic table have been highlighted in its colour, grey.

Figure 1: SALBAGE Logo

1.2 Templates

With this logo, a template for the preparation of the deliverables in format .doc has been distributed among the partners. The present document already complies with that format.

Presentations and other documents will also make use of the logo and brand image of the project.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	4 / 9

3 Webpage

A dedicated webpage has been set as part of the dissemination activities. The page is www.salbageproject.eu. A capture is presented in figure 2.

Figure 2: Capture of the dedicated webpage

The page has been divided in different sections, namely:

- **Home:** With a general description of the project
- **Salbage project (About):** More detailed information of the project advances will be presented here
- **Partners:** Direct link to the partner webpages
- **News/events:** Here all the events and news of the project will be gathered
- **Media/downloads:** Newsletters, press releases and any other public document of general interest will be uploaded here
- **Contact:** Contact info provided here. A contact email has been created at the same domain being info@salbageproject.eu.

Additionally, a **private intranet** platform has been created and each partner has been given a user and password.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	5 / 9

In this private area, shared documents as well as all the documents created such as Minutes, meeting's agenda etc. will be uploaded for all the partners to have access to.

In figures 3 to 5 the intranet area is presented. All partners received a personal username and password in order to log in the intranet.

All the deliverables and technical reports as well as the presentations of the meetings are continually uploaded to this private zone.

Figure 3: Capture of the dedicated webpage featuring the Intranet Access

Figure 4: Login in the intranet

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	6 / 9

Figure 5: Intranet private area

4 Social Networks

Different social networks profiles have been created in a combination that is aimed to reach the widest possible audience, from purely scientific network such as Researchgate, to general public such as Twitter.

4.1 ResearchGate

This network that gathers the scientific community is the perfect environment for scientific discussion and to share deep knowledge on the matter, such as scientific breakthroughs and advances. Within this network, the scientific publications, open source, will be shared.

The set profile in this network is the following: <https://www.researchgate.net/project/SALBAGE-FET-OPEN-Project>. And its preview is presented in figure 6.

Figure 6: Capture of the Researchgate page.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	7 / 9

This project has received funding from the **EU H2020-FETOPEN-2016-2017** Grant Agreement N^o**766581**. This document and its content is **CONFIDENTIAL** unless otherwise stated according to the EU rules and GA terms.

4.2 LinkedIn

This network gathers professionals from all sectors. A profile of the project has been created here with the aim of reaching professionals in the battery and related industries in order to raise awareness on potential future technologies such as the Sulfur-Aluminium that SALBAGE project wants to develop.

The LinkedIn profile address is <https://www.linkedin.com/company/salbage-project-fetopen/>

The page will be continuously fed with relevant news on the project and related technologies, in a more plain language for the general public to understand. A preview is shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Preview of the LinkedIn profile.

4.3 Twitter

Last, but not least, a twitter account named @Salbage_project has been created in the most generalist network, Twitter. From this account general news and events will be released. In addition, relevant news on the sector will be published here.

The twitter account is https://twitter.com/SALBAGE_Project and a preview is shown in figure 8.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	8 / 9

Figure 8: Preview of the Twitter profile

In order to reach a greater audience on Twitter, other accounts such as @fet_eu and those of the partners will be included in the tweets. Also appropriate hashtags such as #FETOPEN, #H2020 or similar will be used along with the any other suitable depending on the context.

5 Conclusions and final remarks.

A variety of actions have been carried out in order to provide the due visibility and projection to the SALBAGE project.

Along with the creation of a logo and brand image of the project, different accounts in various networks have been set. All these accounts will be continuously fed in the frame of the diffusion activities of the project during and beyond the project life.

Special use of these tools will be made whenever relevant news related to the project happens, such as project meetings, participation in events etc, as well as when any significant advance or breakthrough takes place.

Additionally related news on the field of batteries, or related topics as well as other news regarding EU policies and FET-Open will be shared from these accounts. Besides, and in order to make a greater impact and reach a wider audience on the shared news, most probably LinkedIn and Twitter will be linked for the two accounts to provide feedback news on each other.

TYPE	Dissemination Level	NAME	REFERENCE			PAGE
			Document ID	Edition/revision	DATE	
DEC	PU	Launch of webpage, branding and logo	D1.1-PU-01-2017	02/00	10/02/2019	9 / 9